

Welcome Royal International Global LLC with new guidelines

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Dear Colleagues,

It gives us an immense pleasure to release the first issue of Royal International Global Journal of Advance and Applied Research (RIJAAR) for the year 2024 in your hands published by international publishers, Royal International Global LLC. RIJAAR is an official publication of the Royal International Global LLC (RIGLLC). Researchers from all across the globe have recognized this Journal and have been keenly looking forward for new editions. Now, with the publishers like Royal International Global LLC, you will get good service. Better quality and high standard articles are expected from all of you to get better visibility in the scientific arena.

This issue has a review article by: *Dr. Praveen G Saptarshi, Dr. Daneshwar. R. Pandey, Dr. Lal Mervin Dharmasiri, Dr. Sambhaji D. Shinde, Dr. Harish. B. Tipe, Dr. Gajanan Ghodake, Dr. Munther Moh'd Ibrahim Zyoud and Dr. F. M. Nadaf*

Review-1

“Impact of Lending Practices on the Adoption of Green Banking Practices for the Sustainable Development”

The paper investigated the feasibility of green banking practices particularly for lending. The study has formulated two hypotheses. One attempts to understand the impact of green practices and the other by adopting electronic based lending practices. The second hypothesis that there is significant impact of electronic based lending practice on adoption of green banking has been accepted with appropriate methodology. The paper has been useful to understand the interplay between lending practices and adoption of banking principles. Most importantly, the present study has good relevance for policy makers, financial institutions and several stakeholders in the sector. It also shows concern about environmental and social sustainability goals. The study is based on primary data and hence has attempted to explain the ground truth.

Considering methodology, primary data and relevant topic it is strongly recommended for publication.

Review By

Dr. Daneshwar. R. Pandey

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Review-2

“The Impact of Global Trade Policies on Developing Economies”

The study presented in the paper is trying to surface the issues of international trade, policies of which are guided by the market forces and international relationship. Both bilateral and multilateral trades put forth some opportunities and issues as well. The most vulnerable stakeholders come from developing countries. They are impacted negatively by global trade policies encompassing tariffs, quotas and trade agreements. The developing countries are characterised by low-income levels, less industrialisation and higher dependence on agriculture. For achieving climate resilience, it is necessary to reduce the trade risks. However, volatile global market has posed significant challenges according to the authors. The study has given the case study of South Korea exhibiting the success story how integrated approach of investing in education and achieving innovations in electronics have made the country a leading exporter of electronic goods. For comparative analysis the study has chosen the case study of struggling economy of Malwai. It has encountered significant hurdles, such as limited infrastructure, dependency on a narrow range of exports and difficulties in meeting international standards. The country's reliance on tobacco exports makes it highly vulnerable to fluctuations in global demand and prices, leading to economic instability and slow growth. Thus, the paper concludes that global trade policies have significant and varied impacts on developing economies. While they can provide opportunities for growth, innovation, and employment, they also pose risks related to market volatility, deindustrialization and trade imbalances. The paper urges that future global trade policies should involve regional cooperation and focus on sustainable development. The paper also warns that developing countries have to face the situations created due to challenging trade liberalization.

The paper has explained the intricacies of the problems faced by developing countries by adopting a case study approach. Overall presentation is good. Therefore, it is worth to have space in the international publication.

Review By

Prof. Lal Mervin Dharmasiri

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Review-3

“Analyzing Post-COVID Challenges: Strategies for Crisis Preparedness and Mental Health Support”

There are several studies on the issues put forth by Covid pandemic. Several scholars have opined on the social, economic, political factors attributed to the deprivation of health care services to some sections of population worldwide. This paper has also explained the impact of Covid and the reasons thereby. The study explains how rapid spread of Covid-19 affected almost all the countries due to closure of economy, drastic change in social behavior and how the world was caught off guard. The healthcare systems collapsed and the spread of virus was uncontrolled for some months. Apart from these immediate impacts the long-term implications of the pandemic and the formidable challenges were quite serious. The post-COVID era showed unambiguous reminder of the interconnection of our biosphere and the potentials for infectious Trans boundary transfer of diseases. Post-COVID Challenges as revealed in the study are 1. Socio-Economic Disparities, 2. Healthcare Systems Strain and 3. Mental Health Crisis. Based on literature study author has also suggested the strategies for crisis preparedness. The paper gives strong warning regarding the crisis management should be based on international cooperation. I would have been better to support the statements with appropriate data. However, the paper has documented the event in the articulate manner and hence recommended for publication.

Review By

Dr. Sambhaji D. Shinde

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Review-4

“Sustainable Agricultural Development through Modern Micro-Irrigation Technology”

It is well problem that Indian agriculture faces problem of water scarcity. The paper suggests solution to by adopting new technology like sprinkler and drip irrigation system. It is well known fact that drip irrigation system saves about 90% water and sprinkler, about 65%. The scholar, trained in economics has given the account of how these micro irrigation systems have gained grounds in Australia and South Africa and thereafter to several countries including India. The paper claims that adoption of such technologies can extend irrigation areas by 5%. However, the cost benefit analysis of the new technology would have thrown some light on question why there is very low acceptance to the technology. However, this descriptive study has its own importance and hence the present reviewer recommends its publication.

Review By

Dr. Gajanan Ghodake

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Review-5

Current Global Issues: A Review with Wide Coverage

The paper under review aims to understand and study the major global issues at conceptual level. Obviously, the presentation is descriptive based on secondary information. The paper attempts to highlight the multifaceted current global issues and how they are interconnected, why they need comprehensive attention and coordinated efforts. Thus, the study tries to address these issues especially in the context of climate change and related threats to mankind like rising global temperatures, extreme weather events, and sea-level rise, degradation of ecosystems, human settlements and economies especially vulnerable economies. The scholar states in the beginning that COVID-19 pandemic has underlined the vulnerability of global health systems and the urgent need for better preparedness and equitable access to healthcare. Moreover, economic inequality is widening, with significant disparities in income and wealth distribution within and between countries, leading to social and financial instability. This is clearly observed in our country. There are about eighteen issues briefly described in the paper. I think the present state of world economy and world polity has to be changed to address such issues and most importantly, democracies in each country must be strengthened.

The paper is worth to be published in the journal.

Review By

Munther Moh'd Ibrahim Zyoud

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Review-6

“Infrared Spectroscopical Analysis of Some Metamorphic (Granite) Rocks”

The paper is devoted to underline the importance of infrared spectroscopic analysis of granitic terrain in Tamilnadu to understand the method by itself and geological value of the area. The investigator has adopted scientific approach right from selection and collection of samples to use of infrared spectroscopic method. The selected rock samples are granite. The mineral characters of metamorphic rocks are tremolite, kyanite, stautolite, talc, serpentine, mica and chlorite. Infrared spectroscopy is one of the foremost capable explanatory strategies which offer chemical distinguishing proof and is a powerful tool in identifying quantitative and qualitative analysis of the minerals present in geological samples. The experiment has indicated the presence of quartz, feldspar, diapside, garnet and chlorite minerals. The obtained results are tabulated and interpreted in light of available literature with special reference to crystallinity index, absorbance and extinction coefficient. The paper is worth to be published to expose young geologists to learn the technique and learned academicians to appreciate or to find out lacuna if any.

Review By

Dr. F. M. Nadaf

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Review Report...

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The first issue of the “Royal International Global Journal of Advance and Applied Research” a journal with Royal International Global LLC gives you the detailed instructions of how to submit an article to the Journal, it must be original article with, a review, case report, or others. Please read the instructions carefully and follow them correctly before uploading your article to the Journal’s website. If you do not send the article according to the instructions, the article will come back with an editorial review stating you to follow and modify the article, which will result in a delay in processing the article. Please upload your article using this link <https://rlgjaar.com/archives> as an author, after registering yourself as an author. Everything is time bound, and your articles will be processed accordingly.

We hope you will enjoy reading this issue, and you can send me your comments in the form of letters to the editor.

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